

ENES CDI Strategic Requirements

A white paper setting out strategic requirements of the European Network for Earth System Modelling (ENES) Climate Data Infrastructure (CDI).

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1. Introduction

The ENES (European Network for Earth System Modelling) Climate Data Infrastructure (CDI) Strategic Requirements build on the [CDI Mission and Objectives](#) [hereafter MO], providing an additional level of detail reflecting specific activities which are considered necessary to fulfil those objectives. The MO provides more background on ENES. These strategic requirements are split into three elements which cover different aspects of the collaborative enterprise. The first gives an overview of community requirements, at a strategic level, and their relation to our mission and objectives. That is, a review of the different capabilities, such as bulk movement of data, quality control, and type of access, such as data download versus server access, rather than of the specific requirements around the implementation of services. There will also be discussion of the communities involved. The second element of the strategic requirements discusses community projects through which services are delivered. The final element deals with foundational service elements which enable service delivery, exploiting and advancing best practice in data services.

Community Requirements

The first element of the strategic requirements deals with the need to communicate and operate effectively as an organisation embedded in a diverse, active and evolving research community.

Open Science, FAIR and Trusted Data

The **FAIR Data** guidelines provide a clear and accessible reference for best practice in data services. The ENES CDI will continue to provide leadership in the creation of services which implement the guidelines fully. The ENES CDI will promote Open Science [EC_opsci,

EC_opsci_fs, WP_opsci], making scientific products and processes accessible to a broad user community (see below) and reusable, by making data and tools accessible through a variety of well documented services. Implementation of FAIR principles [wilkinsonetal_2016, f11_fair] requires work in areas of technical implementation and engagement with both user and provider communities. This work is being addressed directly in several of the collaborative projects introduced below. The CoreTrustSeal provides a globally recognised standard for trustworthy repositories: the ENES CDI exploits and champions these standards, implementing them operationally and promoting efforts to bring key data from Earth System Models into CoreTrust Seal approved repositories¹.

Developing Strategy for Sustainable Services

The ENES CDI hosts discussions and leads on delivering coordinated European data services for the Earth system modelling community. Continuity of services is an essential foundation for building and maintaining trust in the data user and data provider communities, but the services must also adapt to the rapidly evolving needs and expectations of the user communities and exploit the multiple opportunities of new data management and analysis technologies.

Engaging with the Scientific Communities

The ENES CDI exists to support the climate modelling community, both through direct provision of services for that community and through the dissemination of climate model data to the climate science community and to additional user communities, notably the climate change assessment, mitigation, impacts, adaptation and climate services communities. Proactive engagement is needed both to ensure that these target communities understand the services available and to obtain a robust understanding of the complex requirements of the users.

European RI Creation and Integration

The ENES CDI will engage in governance and strategic activities to strengthen and maintain the ENES Climate Data Infrastructure, working with the Board of Environmental Research Infrastructures (BEERi). We will also develop service delivery projects with other European Research Infrastructures (RIs) to exploit synergies and improve the dissemination of data to a broader user community. The Horizon 2020 project IS-ENES3 is developing a sustainable RI.

Communications, Training and Outreach

Communications cut across all aspects of work in the ENES CDI, and include communication with stakeholders and with a range of user communities. The aims are:

¹ DKRZ and CEDA have CoreTrust Seal status, IPSL is in process of registering [status 2022]

- To make the tools, standards, etc. known to a broader group of potential users. This goes beyond the group of climate scientists. We also target other potential users such as impact researchers and climate service providers. In some parts of Europe and the world the work of the ENES CDI may be less known: communication and outreach activities also focus on reaching people in these countries
- To train new/young scientists in the use of the tools, standards, portals, etc. Knowing that certain tools, standards, portals, etc. exist is often not enough to profit from this. Therefore, short and longer training sessions are organised to get people more acquainted. This also helps create a network that can help these young/new scientists after the trainings
- To obtain feedback from users on gaps and weaknesses in the ENES CDI services.

Collaborative Projects

The second element of the strategic requirements is more focussed on delivery of measurable benefits for the RI user communities. The twin foci of data interoperability and global climate change lead to a strong requirement for global international collaboration. The ENES CDI works with many partners through a range of collaborative frameworks, many of which are framed through programmes and activities of international organisations such as the World Climate Research Programme and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. The form of participation will vary for each activity, with membership of international teams taking the form of participation by ENES partners rather than through a direct membership of ENES. This might change in future through efforts to formalise the legal status of IS-ENES in the ongoing sustainability process.

The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP)

The ENES CDI is responsible for the publication of CMIP data from European modelling centres and replication data from other centres to Europe to support scientific analysis. We provide leadership in the global collaboration supporting data services for CMIP through engagement in planning, design and delivery by participating in key coordinating bodies (WGCM Infrastructure Panel - WIP; Climate Data Node Operations Team - CDNOT).

CORDEX: Regional Climate Modelling

The ENES CDI also supports the publication of the European contribution to the CORDEX programme and the efforts of science teams led from Europe. It provides leadership in the global collaboration supporting CORDEX through participation in planning, design and delivery.

Where reasonable requirements from our users go beyond the current scope of available scientific information (e.g. as for quantification and mitigation of model bias), we will engage with the scientific community to seek improvements.

The Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF)

The Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) is the delivery mechanism for CMIP and a range of other international climate modelling projects. The ENES CDI both exploits ESGF to ensure that data is disseminated efficiently to the international community and contributes to ESGF development and operation to ensure that the infrastructure remains effective. We engage in governance and management bodies (ESGF Executive Committee and Steering Committee).

Earth System Documentation (ES-DOC)

The ES-DOC system captures and disseminates the documentation of models, experimental specification and experimental conformances. It provides a globally recognised platform for structured hosting and provides access to documentation of ESMs and ESM computations. The ENES CDI both exploits ES-DOC to ensure that data is disseminated efficiently to the international community and leads ES-DOC development and operation to ensure that the infrastructure remains effective.

IPCC Data Distribution Centre (DDC)

The IPCC DDC (www.ipcc-data.org, [juckesetal_2020]) provides data service support for the IPCC assessment process, spanning physical climate data from models, observations and analysis, data on environmental processes and impacts, and social and economic datasets related to the drivers of, impact of and response to climate change.

Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)

ENES CDI services and expertise has supported the creation of the European flagship climate service, C3S, in many ways. The delivery of services is funded through contracts issued by C3S, but the quality and effectiveness of the services related to climate projections relies heavily on preparatory work done and the technical expertise and capabilities developed by the ENES community.

A platform for the climate impacts research community

Continued support for climate4impact² is provided by ENES CDI, as a new open source platform for supporting the climate impacts research community, working collaboratively with a range of other projects. The climate impacts research community is highly diverse and heterogeneous, often outside the climate science domain. Activities include promoting the adoption of FAIR technologies and guidelines within this community, especially with regards to documentation, development of methods and their reproducibility, both for the benefit of these users and to foster appropriate citation of underlying climate model data.

² Version 2, <https://dev.climate4impact.eu/> is being developed to replace version 1, <https://climate4impact.eu> [both accessed 2022-04-07].

Foundations

The final element of the strategic requirements deals with foundational aspects of the infrastructure which are needed to ensure robust and efficient operations. These foundations may be unobtrusive, often by design, but may nevertheless involve considerable collaborative effort. This element includes services which reflect lines of activity within the data service community and cut across multiple user facing projects.

Data Curation

Scalable and authoritative data services must be built on a solid foundation of well curated data. The ENES CDI seeks to enforce all aspects of the data curation standards set by the climate modelling activities. For CMIP this includes checks on the compliance with CF Conventions, with the CMIP protocol, and checks on the consistency of the time axis data and metadata.

Data Standards and Tools

Both for the exchange of data within the community and the dissemination beyond, data standards play an essential role. The ENES CDI provides international leadership in promoting and developing standards which can support the rapidly evolving requirements of the climate modelling research community. This involves work on domain standards such as the Climate and Forecast Convention (CF), Earth-System Documentation (ES-DOC) and the CMIP Data Request, as well as engagement in broader activities such as the Research Data Alliance.

Data Service Monitoring and Service Standards

Data services are delivered through a federated infrastructure which provides resilience and flexibility. Service monitoring is needed both to ensure effective delivery and for reporting to stakeholders.

A broad range of metrics is provided by the ESGF Data Statistics monitoring service, giving strong feedback on how end-users exploit the ESGF federation and to what extent, in terms of both downloaded and published data. This type of monitoring gives insights into the most/less accessed data, highlighting the level of interest of the community in specific data but also gathering some key information on the long tail of research.

Information Technology Infrastructure

The ENES CDI needs a scalable and sustainable information technology (IT) infrastructure providing facilities, networking, storage, servers, and infrastructure management tools and services. The IT infrastructure needs to support scalable services for data movement, management (including curation), analysis and download, dealing with high data volumes and large and diverse user communities.

Data Processing Services

Users cannot be expected to exploit the full range of data products available by downloading them onto their own machines. The creation of individual copies of data by multiple users is both inefficient use of their time and wasteful of hardware resources and the energy needed to keep hardware running.

Licensing and Citation

All data products, software tools and standards documents should have clear licences and citation guidance. The data citation service gives users the information they need to provide accurate citation of the data that they have used. Data providers have, in the past, felt that the CMIP archive obscured their ownership of data. The CMIP6 Data Citation Service ensures that the ENES CDI services comply with best practice and meet the FAIR2FAIR criteria for FAIR data, giving users clear and functional information about data provenance.

Appendix A: Glossary

Climate model: The term "climate model" here refers to numerical models used for quantitative **simulation** of the interactions of the important drivers of climate, including atmosphere, oceans, land surface, ice and parts of the biosphere. Climate models which include the carbon cycle are often referred to as **Earth System Models** to distinguish them from climate models which use prescribed atmospheric carbon dioxide concentrations. The term General Circulation Model is used for climate models which include representations of the circulation in both atmosphere and oceans (also referred to as "coupled models", as in "coupled model intercomparison project").

Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S): C3S provides authoritative information about the past, present and future climate, as well as tools to enable climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies by policy makers and businesses (<https://climate.copernicus.eu/>).

CoreTrustSeal of the International Science Council World Data System (WDS). <https://www.coretrustseal.org/why-certification/certified-repositories/>.

Digital Infrastructure (sometimes "e-infrastructure" or "cyberinfrastructure" [US]) : "environments that support advanced data acquisition, data storage, data management, data integration, data mining, data visualization and other computing and information processing services distributed over the Internet beyond the scope of a single institution" (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cyberinfrastructure>).

Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) : A global international collaboration and digital infrastructure (<https://esgf.llnl.gov/> and <https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/projects/esgf-llnl/>).

Earth System Documentation (ES-DOC): <https://es-doc.org/>

ESGF Data Statistics Service: <http://esgf-ui.cmcc.it/esgf-dashboard-ui/index.html>

Earth System Models (ESMs): Earth system models (ESMs) are climate models which combine atmosphere–ocean models with "models of other climate-related systems, such as the land surface, the cryosphere (glaciers, sea ice, and snow cover), hydrology (lakes, rivers, evaporation, and rainfall), and vegetation" (Edwards, 2010) to represent the carbon cycle.

European Strategy forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) supports a coherent and strategy-led approach to policy-making on research infrastructures in Europe, and facilitates multilateral initiatives leading to the better use and development of research infrastructures, at EU and international level. ESFRI categorise research infrastructures according to the maturity of their intergovernmental status and their services. **Landmark** RIs are either operational or in the implementation phase, RI projects progress through concept, design or preparation phases. <https://www.esfri.eu/>

FAIR Data: The FAIR Data principles are a concise and measurable set of principles that are intended to act as a guideline for those wishing to enhance the reusability of their data holdings [wilkinsonetal_2016]. The principles have been adopted and elaborated by **Force 11** [forec11 fair data], and their implementation is supported by **Go-FAIR**.

FORCE 11: "a community of scholars, librarians, archivists, publishers and research funders that has arisen organically to help facilitate the change toward improved knowledge creation and sharing." (<https://www.force11.org/about>)

Go-FAIR: An initiative from EU Member States (self-described as "bottom-up", but governed by ministerial representatives from participating EU countries) to promote the adoption of FAIR data principles. <https://www.go-fair.org>

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC): www.ipcc.ch

Open Science: "Open Science is a system change allowing for better science through open and collaborative ways of producing and sharing knowledge and data" (EC Open Science Fact Sheet, 2019) and is a policy priority for the European Commission (EC Open Science Policy). Often referred to as open scholarship or open research in the arts and humanities, it is a movement to make science accessible to all parts of society (Wikipedia).

Simulation: A simulation here refers to the execution of an experiment by a climate model.

WCRP: The World Climate Research Programme coordinates and facilitates international climate research to develop, share, and apply the climate knowledge that contributes to societal well-being. (<https://www.wcrp-climate.org/>)

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